

COSMOS-Web: stellar mass assembly in relation to dark matter halos across $0.2 < z < 12$ of cosmic history

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Received ; accepted

ABSTRACT

We study the stellar mass assembly of galaxies via the stellar mass function (SMF) and the co-evolution with dark matter halos via abundance matching in the largest redshift range to date $0.2 < z < 12$. We use the 0.53 deg^2 imaged by *JWST* from the COSMOS-Web survey, in combination with ancillary imaging in over 30 photometric bands to select highly complete samples (down to $\log M_*/M_\odot = 7.5 - 8.8$) in 15 redshift bins. Our results show that the normalization of the SMF monotonically decreases from $z = 0.2$ to $z = 12$ with strong mass-dependent evolution. At $z > 5$, we find increased abundances of massive ($\log M_*/M_\odot > 10.5$) systems compared to predictions from semi-analytical models and hydrodynamical simulations. These findings challenge traditional galaxy formation models by implying integrated star formation efficiencies (SFE) $\epsilon_* \equiv M_* f_b^{-1} M_{\text{halo}}^{-1} \gtrsim 0.5$. We find a flattening of the SMF at the high-mass end that is better described by a double power law at $z > 5.5$, after correcting for the Eddington bias. At $z \lesssim 5.5$ it transitions to a Schechter law which coincides with the emergence of the first massive quiescent galaxies in the Universe, indicating that physical mechanisms that suppress galaxy growth start to take place at $z \sim 5.5$ on a global scale. By integrating the SMF, we trace the cosmic stellar mass density (SMD) and infer the star formation rate density (SFRD), which at $z > 7.5$ agrees remarkably with recent *JWST* UV luminosity function-derived estimates. This agreement solidifies the emerging picture of rapid galaxy formation leading to increased abundances of bright and massive galaxies in the first ~ 0.7 Gyrs. However, at $z \lesssim 3.5$, we find significant tension (~ 0.3 dex) with the cosmic star formation (SF) history from instantaneous SF measures, the causes of which remain poorly understood. We infer the stellar-to-halo mass relation (SHMR) and the SFE from abundance matching out to $z = 12$, finding a non-monotonic evolution. The SFE has the characteristic strong dependence with mass in the range of $0.02 - 0.2$, and mildly decreases at the low mass end out to $z \sim 3.5$. At $z \sim 3.5$ there is an upturn and the SFE increases sharply from ~ 0.1 to approach high SFE of $0.8 - 1$ by $z \sim 10$ for $\log(M_h/M_\odot) \approx 11.5$, albeit with large uncertainties. Finally, we use the SHMR to track the SFE and stellar mass growth throughout the halo history and find that they do not grow at the same rate – from the earliest times up until $z \sim 3.5$ the halo growth rate outpaces galaxy assembly, but at $z > 3.5$ halo growth stagnates and accumulated gas reservoirs keep the SF going and galaxies outpace halos.

Key words. galaxies: evolution – galaxies: statistics – galaxies: luminosity function, mass function – galaxies: high-redshift

Supplementary online only materials: Appendices

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Appendix A: Mass uncertainty kernels

Fig. A.1: Kernels used in accounting for the Eddington bias for each redshift bin. These are constructed by stacking the $\text{PDF}(M_*)$ of all sources in the redshift bin.

Figure A.1 shows the distributions of stellar mass uncertainties obtained by stacking the $\text{PDF}(M_*)$, centered at the median of the distribution, for each redshift bin. The distributions are therefore shown as a function of $M_* - \langle M_* \rangle$, where $\langle M_* \rangle$ is the median of $\text{PDF}(M_*)$. The width of the distribution increases with redshift, quantifying the increasing stellar mass uncertainties with redshift.

Appendix B: Properties of removed AGN/LRD

20 Figure B.1 shows the distribution of several properties of the AGN/LRD population that we exclude from our analysis (cf. §??). The $m_{F277W} - m_{F444W}$ color distribution shows a bimodality because of our double criterion to identify the AGN/LRD population: Red \wedge Compact and AGN-SED \wedge Compact. With respect to the z_{phot} solution, they are distributed within the $4 \lesssim z \lesssim 9$ range, with a mode at $z \sim 8$. The middle right panel shows that it is mostly the Red \wedge Compact criterion that selects at $z \sim 8$. The stellar mass distribution of the AGN/LRD population, weighted by the volume in $3.5 < z < 12$ and compared to the total SMF, is shown in the bottom right panel of Fig. B.1. The relative contribution of the AGN/LRD to the SMF becomes more important at the high mass end, therefore not removing this population would lead to higher number densities at $z > 4$ and $\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.5$.

Fig. B.1: Distribution of properties of the AGN/LRD removed from the primary scientific analysis.

Appendix C: The SMF in the MIRI-covered area

Fig. C.1: The SMF in the full COSMOS-Web (orange) and in the MIRI-covered area (blue). The downward pointing arrows show the upper limits for empty bins. The agreement between the two shows that the masses are consistent when including MIRI photometry.

Figure C.1 shows the SMF measured in the area covered by MIRI F770W. After excluding the HSC star masks, this results in 0.15 deg^2 . Not all sources that enter our analysis in the MIRI coverage would have a F770W counterpart above the 5σ depth of AB mag ~ 25.7 . Nonetheless, we consider sources with $S/N < 5$ as even non-detections can provide useful constraints in the SED fitting.

Appendix D: Examples of the most extreme objects in our sample and their color properties

Fig. D.1: Color vs. magnitude distribution of the extreme sample, defined as $M_{\star} > \text{med}(M_{\star}^{\text{max}})$ (derived from the EVS formalism), color coded by $E(B - V)$. Diamonds show the SMGs from the SCUBADive sample.

Figure D.1 shows the F277W – F444W color vs magnitude distribution for the sources in our extreme sample, defined as $M_{\star} > \text{med}(M_{\star}^{\text{max}})$, color coded by $E(B - V)$. Diamonds mark the SCUBADive (McKinney et al. 2024) detected SMGs. A significant fraction ($> 50\%$) of our extreme sample is very red ($m_{\text{F277W}} - m_{\text{F444W}} > 1$) and dust attenuated ($E(B - V) > 0.5$). Fig. D.2 shows examples of two of the most extreme sources in our sample according to the EVS analysis (cf. ??). In each of the top three rows we show the science, model and residual images of 4 arcsec size in several selected broad bands. The middle row shows the science images of bands used in the SED fitting. In the bottom left panel, we show the photometry (blue points) and the LEPHARE SEDs of the best fit galaxy template (orange), star template (gray), and QSO template (purple). The open orange circles indicate the flux of the best-fit SED integrated in the corresponding filter. The top right panel shows the resulting photo- z distribution.

ID = 762429; RA, Dec = 150.421658, 2.195859

Appendix E: Galaxy candidates at $10 < z < 12$

In Fig. E.1 we show the distribution of some of the properties of the $10 < z < 12$ galaxy candidates in our work, and discussed in more detail in §?? and §??.

Fig. E.1: Distribution of some of the properties of the $10 < z < 12$ galaxy candidates in our work. The right-most panel shows the $P(z)$ of all $10 < z < 12$ candidates in transparent orange, while the solid orange shows the median stack of all.

Appendix F: Comparison with CIGALE

Fig. F.1: Comparison of the stellar masses from the different SED modelling by LEPHARE and CIGALE. The figure shows the difference in the $\log(M_*/M_\odot)$ between CIGALE and LEPHARE as a function of the LEPHARE mass. Each panel corresponds to the 15 z -bins in which we measure the SMF.

Fig. F.2: The resulting SMF using CIGALE M_* (brown histogram), compared to the nominal SMF of this paper measured from LEPHARE masses (square with errorbars).

To assess the robustness of our results, we ran CIGALE¹ (Boquien et al. 2019) to estimate the physical parameters independently. CIGALE is a Bayesian-like analysis code that models the entire SED of galaxies from the X-rays to radio by adopting the energy budget balance between the UV-optical emission from young stars and absorption and re-emission by dust in IR. The SED modelling with CIGALE and the resulting performance is described in detail in Arango-Toro et al. (2024). Briefly, CIGALE is run to fit only for physical parameters by fixing the redshift on the z_{phot} solution from LEPHARE. It implements the sfnLevels non-parametric SFH module with a bursty continuity prior (presented and tested in Ciesla et al. 2023, see also Arango-Toro et al. 2023), the stellar population models (SSPs) of Bruzual & Charlot (2003) and the Dale et al. (2014) dust emission library. The dust attenuation is a modified Calzetti et al. (2000) law, which implements a modified starburst law with the continuum attenuated with the Calzetti et al. (2000) curve and the lines extinguished with a Milky Way or a Magellanic Cloud attenuation curve; the allowed $E(B - V)$ range is 0 – 1.8. We note that the attenuation modeling is different than our nominal LEPHARE run that uses three different attenuation curves but with a more limited $E(B - V)$ range of 0 – 1.2.

This SED modelling, most notably the dust attenuation and the non-parametric SFH, allows us to estimate how our results on the measurements of M_* and the SMF would be affected by SED modelling. However, we note that the fact that z_{phot} is fixed at the solution from LEPHARE limits the full and independent exploration of SED solutions by CIGALE.

¹ <https://cigale.lam.fr/>

Figure F.1 compares M_* by the two codes in the 15 redshift bins. This shows a constant bias towards higher M_* inferred by CIGALE that is dependent on both redshift and mass. The difference is about 0.1 at $z < 0.5$ and $\sim 0.2 - 0.3$ at higher redshifts. With respect to the mass, the difference is higher at the low-mass end and decreases with mass out to $z \sim 5.5$. At $z > 5.5$ this trend reverses and CIGALE results in higher masses with increasing LE-PHARE mass by about 0.1 – 0.3 dex.

Figure F.2 shows how these differences propagate into the SMF and capture the variance and uncertainty arising from different SED modelling assumptions. Interestingly, however, our findings of increased abundances of massive galaxies at $z \gtrsim 5$ are corroborated by the SED modelling by CIGALE.

Appendix G: Fitting results

Table G.1 presents the parameter values of the double/single Schechter and double power law models, derived as the median, 16th and 84th percentiles of the posterior distribution.

Table G.1: Values of the double/single Schechter and double power law model parameters. At $z > 3.5$ we show the parameters for both single Schechter and DPL.

z -bin	N_{gal}	$\text{Log}_{10} M^*$ (M_{\odot})	$\log \Phi_1$ ($\text{Mpc}^{-3} \text{dex}^{-1}$)	α_1	$\log \Phi_2$ ($\text{Mpc}^{-3} \text{dex}^{-1}$)	α_2	BIC	$\log(\rho_{\star})$ ($M_{\odot} \text{Mpc}^{-3}$)
0.2 < z < 0.5	19092							
Double Schechter		10.78 ^{+0.12} _{-0.15}	-3.19 ^{+0.19} _{-0.30}	-1.52 ^{+0.06} _{-0.08}	-2.67 ^{+0.16} _{-0.21}	-0.52 ^{+0.62} _{-0.34}	10.73	8.27 ^{+0.07} _{-0.08}
0.5 < z < 0.8	40107							
Double Schechter		10.73 ^{+0.07} _{-0.10}	-3.43 ^{+0.26} _{-0.33}	-1.62 ^{+0.09} _{-0.11}	-2.70 ^{+0.11} _{-0.14}	-0.70 ^{+0.45} _{-0.22}	7.77	8.15 ^{+0.06} _{-0.07}
0.8 < z < 1.1	44742							
Double Schechter		10.73 ^{+0.09} _{-0.13}	-2.99 ^{+0.16} _{-0.22}	-1.40 ^{+0.05} _{-0.07}	-2.76 ^{+0.14} _{-0.16}	-0.60 ^{+0.62} _{-0.31}	8.54	8.21 ^{+0.06} _{-0.06}
1.1 < z < 1.5	40801							
Double Schechter		10.58 ^{+0.12} _{-0.10}	-3.16 ^{+0.11} _{-0.18}	-1.42 ^{+0.04} _{-0.06}	-2.93 ^{+0.11} _{-0.10}	0.20 ^{+0.55} _{-0.65}	9.22	7.96 ^{+0.06} _{-0.07}
1.5 < z < 2.0	55635							
Double Schechter		10.66 ^{+0.13} _{-0.13}	-3.37 ^{+0.14} _{-0.21}	-1.53 ^{+0.05} _{-0.07}	-3.10 ^{+0.13} _{-0.15}	-0.17 ^{+0.61} _{-0.57}	8.59	7.85 ^{+0.06} _{-0.07}
2.0 < z < 2.5	32602							
Double Schechter		10.73 ^{+0.09} _{-0.11}	-3.58 ^{+0.14} _{-0.18}	-1.54 ^{+0.05} _{-0.07}	-3.34 ^{+0.13} _{-0.13}	-0.44 ^{+0.53} _{-0.39}	10.09	7.68 ^{+0.06} _{-0.06}
2.5 < z < 3.0	18886							
Double Schechter		10.67 ^{+0.15} _{-0.16}	-3.80 ^{+0.19} _{-0.26}	-1.58 ^{+0.06} _{-0.09}	-3.56 ^{+0.17} _{-0.19}	-0.45 ^{+0.65} _{-0.44}	8.61	7.43 ^{+0.07} _{-0.09}
3.0 < z < 3.5	13059							
Double Schechter		10.75 ^{+0.17} _{-0.21}	-4.02 ^{+0.22} _{-0.8}	-1.59 ^{+0.08} _{-0.14}	-3.62 ^{+0.31} _{-0.22}	-0.51 ^{+0.70} _{-0.45}	4.75	7.39 ^{+0.09} _{-0.12}
3.5 < z < 4.5	14281							
Single Schechter		10.99 ^{+0.18} _{-0.18}	-4.31 ^{+0.19} _{-0.23}	-1.63 ^{+0.07} _{-0.08}	–	–	5.45	7.03 ^{+0.07} _{-0.09}
Double power law		11.00 ^{+0.14} _{-0.16}	-4.06 ^{+0.20} _{-0.20}	-1.68 ^{+0.06} _{-0.06}	–	-5.25 ^{+2.48} _{-2.48}	7.94	
4.5 < z < 5.5	6700							
Single Schechter		11.47 ^{+0.50} _{-0.35}	-5.59 ^{+0.44} _{-0.63}	-1.93 ^{+0.07} _{-0.06}	–	–	2.04	6.62 ^{+0.14} _{-0.11}
Double power law		11.03 ^{+0.49} _{-1.51}	-4.77 ^{+1.69} _{-0.61}	-1.89 ^{+0.29} _{-0.09}	–	-2.91 ^{+3.41} _{-3.41}	3.32	
5.5 < z < 6.5	1974							
Single Schechter		10.93 ^{+0.87} _{-0.50}	-5.64 ^{+0.59} _{-0.92}	-2.00	–	–	-2.04	6.13 ^{+0.17} _{-0.15}
Double power law		10.53 ^{+0.97} _{-0.50}	-4.83 ^{+0.61} _{-1.04}	-2.00	–	-3.35 ^{+3.58} _{-3.58}	-14.24	
6.5 < z < 7.5	1022							
Single Schechter		10.64 ^{+0.94} _{-0.39}	-5.53 ^{+0.47} _{-1.02}	-2.00	–	–	0.59	5.87 ^{+0.18} _{-0.15}
Double power law		10.34 ^{+0.97} _{-0.41}	-4.85 ^{+0.52} _{-1.06}	-2.00	–	-3.68 ^{+3.20} _{-3.20}	-8.71	
7.5 < z < 8.5	704							
Single Schechter		10.01 ^{+0.27} _{-0.22}	-4.92 ^{+0.29} _{-0.38}	-2.00	–	–	0.75	5.67 ^{+0.12} _{-0.14}
Double power law		9.86 ^{+0.21} _{-0.23}	-4.46 ^{+0.31} _{-0.30}	-2.00	–	-4.88 ^{+2.79} _{-2.79}	-5.57	
8.5 < z < 10.0	209							
Single Schechter		11.37 ^{+0.71} _{-0.81}	-6.97 ^{+0.84} _{-0.74}	-2.00	–	–	4.57	5.23 ^{+0.18} _{-0.19}
Double power law		10.90 ^{+0.75} _{-0.71}	-6.13 ^{+0.78} _{-0.76}	-2.00	–	-5.19 ^{+2.66} _{-2.66}	-0.59	
10.0 < z < 12.0	27							
Single Schechter		10.79 ^{+1.12} _{-1.14}	-7.62 ^{+1.39} _{-1.17}	-2.00	–	–	1.33	4.10 ^{+0.35} _{-0.83}
Double power law		10.60 ^{+0.94} _{-0.99}	-7.10 ^{+1.15} _{-0.99}	-2.00	–	-5.52 ^{+2.53} _{-2.53}	1.05	